

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
RESEARCH IN COMPUTER
APPLICATIONS AND ROBOTICS
ISSN 2320-7345

**AN ADAPTIVE TECHNIQUE FOR
ELECTING THE MASTER NODE IN
DISTRIBUTED SYSTEM VIA THE
CLUSTERING PROCESS**

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Abstract

The process of electing the master node in distributed systems is a common problem that requires a huge amount of time. To participate in solving such problem, this research paper presents an improvement version for bully algorithm which bases on clustering concept. The proposed framework divided the distributed system into main cluster and sub cluster, in which the main consists of master and assistant nodes, while sub cluster holds Demaster, Assistant nodes and leaf nodes. The constructed framework reduced the communications overload and single point of failure.

Keywords: Clustering, Distributed System, Bully, Master-Slave, Multiprocessing

1. Introduction

According to memory access process, multiprocessors system can be categorized into centralized and distributed one. Symmetric multiprocessors (i.e. SMPS) defines a computer organization that has a set of identical multiprocessing units connected to a common shared memory, in which all of them have the same ability to reach the system

resources thus the control process for memory is considered a centralized one. Those systems can be used for parallel processing and multithreading problems and applications. The main merits of SMPS is high throughput and more reliability, but at the same time design complexity and memory access controlling are considered as demerits.

On the other hand, asymmetric multiprocessors (i.e. AMPS) defines a computer organization that has a set of identical or non-identical nodes in which one node called master has the responsibility of controlling tasks of other nodes that are called slaves.

Distributed system such as Non-Uniform Memory Access (i.e. NUMA) and Network of workstations (i.e. NOW's) are common examples for those systems [1, 2]. AMPS is characterized by a simple control which is carried out by the master node, minimum collision between resources acquisition is a benefit in those system due to master controlling. Resources utilization, single point of failure and master election or replacement are the main disadvantage of distributed system.

Master election as a common problem in distributed system is the main concern of most researchers. Next leader or master in case of main leader failure is determined by using many different algorithms and techniques that bases on several measures and criteria's such as priority, CPU performance, identifier and address.

Bully algorithm is one of the most simple and clear one to determine the next leader in failure case. It works by giving each node a unique priority identifier which is known by all the nodes in distributed system such that, the main master has the highest priority. If one of the nodes detects that the manager is in a failed state, it sends to the node with the second highest priority. If it responds, the next node takes over the tasks of the main manager until it returns to work. However, if it does not respond, it communicates with the next node and the process of responding or not continues until the next manager is determined [3].

This research suggests a framework for improving availability and performance of master node in distributed system and discusses the main problems that may appear and suggest solutions for them. The proposed model bases on idea of Bully algorithm, it works by dividing the distributed system into subgroups and one main group. The subgroup contains one assistant manager and two assistant nodes to choose the assistant manager in case of his failure in addition to the other normal working nodes. While the

main group contains the assistant managers, the main manager and two assistant nodes to choose the main manager in case of his failure as will be explained later.

2. Related works

The most common known algorithm for election is bully algorithm, in which leader usually is the process with highest identifier [4]. Any request is issued to the leader to execute it. Failure of any processor unless leader will not compose any problem. But leader failure is the problem, when it fails a new election is made. And as said above process with highest identifier is selected. Failure of leader is discovered when it not responds for a requesting process.

Invitation algorithm is another common one, in which a processor declares itself as a leader, and then invites other processors to join its group. Multiple groups may be joined to form a one global group. The following steps show how this algorithm work [5].

- Let P_i the process to be coordinator
- P_i broadcasts an invitation message to all neighbors
- If P_j receives message of P_i then it sends invitation message to all other processes except P_i . It send to P_i an acceptance message
- Now P_j is marked so, it replies with reject to all other invitation messages.

Another common algorithm is ring based algorithm, in which the node that discovered server had crashed, it initializes the election process, it sends its identifier to neighbor process (clock or anti-clock wise) [6]. When process receives the message it compares the received one with its identifier and does the following.

- If received identifier greater than its identifier then
 - o It sends the received one
- Else If received identifier less than its identifier then
 - o It sends its identifier
- Else
 - o It becomes the leader
- End If

3. Materials and Methods

The proposed framework looks to improve the performance of master by decreasing huge amount of communications and availability by suggesting a new election method. In centralized algorithms such as bully algorithm, they use the Master-Slave model in which a single server or a master node is utilized to coordinate the processing operations. Figure.1 shows the form of Master-Slave model, thus any request for data processing or resource allocation is sent via slave node to master. Slaves can communicate with each other to determine the next leader or master in case of master failure. When a slave requires a request from the leader it sends their request and wait specific amount time, if the server not responds then it consider a failure occurred and it must to communicate with others to determine the next expected master. The election algorithm is initiated by the node that discover the failure of master. It sends message to all nodes in system to inform them. The expected master replies to all other by their identity, if no any node sends a confirmation message then the initiator slave becomes the new master. This type of algorithms makes a huge load on master node in term of communication and processing, thus the proposed framework rearrange the system nodes in from to reduce the load of master node as shown in next subsection.

Figure .1: Master-Slave model in distributed system

According to proposed framework that is shown in Figure.2, the nodes of distributed system were divided into five types. The task send roles for each one are explained as follow:

1. **Master Node (i.e. MN)**, which is the main node that exists in the main cluster and manages all processing operations in other clusters by communicating with their master. Also it communicates with their cluster assistant node in order to maintain availability of mastering process.
2. **Master Assistant Node(i.e. MAN)**, which exists in the main cluster and collects information form sub masters and main master in order to construct election operation in case of failure detection at main cluster.
3. **Demaster Node (i.e. DN)**, which is the main node that exists in one of sub clusters and manages all processing operations of their cluster by communicating with the main master node. Also it communicates with their cluster assistant node in order to maintain availability of demastering process.
4. **Demaster Assistant Node(i.e. DAN)**, which exists in the sub cluster and collects information form leaf nodes and Demaster in order to construct election operation in case of failure detection at sub cluster.
5. **Leaf Node (i.e. LN)**, which is member of sub cluster that considered as a working node.

Figure .2: Proposed Framework for distributed system

Each node has a unique priority identifier that is used to distinguish it from all others in distributed system. LN can send two types of requests through the network, one for data processing which is sent to DN and the other for DAN in order to register their self in DAN. More ever, it receives two responds one from DAN in case of failure detection to determine the new Demaster and the other from DN which represents the result of processing. DAN sends request to DN in aim to check their alive and to LN to determine the new leader. Furthermore, it receives information from DN and LN about livein order to make the election process in failure case. DN communicates with DAN about live, LN about processing, MAN about live and MN for an additional processing.

MAN sends request to MN in aim to check their alive and receives information from MN in order to make the election process in failure case. MN communicates with MAN about live and DN for an additional processing.

They are two types of failures that will affect the work of cluster as follow:

1. Demaster failure, it is discovered by LN or DAN, to solve it a local election is initiated by DAN to select a new Demaster. Identifier of new demaster is then sent to the MN and MAN.
2. Master failure, it is discovered by DN or MAN, to solve it the MAN initiates the election process between all DN's to select one of them to become the new DN. In this case an election process also occurs in sub cluster of selected demaster to select a new demaster.

4. Analysis of clustering algorithm

Bully algorithm suffers from single point of failure and huge amount of communication with server. The proposed framework solves or minimizes those problem through distributing nodes into clusters and work in decentralized form.

In term of communication overload, it constructs a system that has multi servers such that each cluster has a local server that computes and process the local request if data hit or available locally. In case of data missing only the DN communicates with MN not LF as in classic Master-Slave model thus the overload on communication network will distributed between different networks that exist between MN with DN and DN with LN.

Single point of failure was manipulated in this frame work locally and globally. Locally DAN's collect information's from DN and different LN's in aim to use them for

next Demaster. Each sub cluster has two DAN's in order to improve availability of Demaster and cluster working. On the side, the main cluster has two MAN's that are collect information from MN and different DN's, those information will be used in the future selecting the new master in case failure detection.

In general, the proposed framework is classified as robust against communication overload due to tasks distribution between several servers and also robust against failure due to election process that bases on collecting information about every node in the system.

5. Conclusion

As we saw above applying clustering technique will give a good performance rather than bully in term of communication overload and failure detection process. In our life, nothing without cost, you will improve performance by minimizing communication request and distributing tasks between different servers, but you will need for further management which needs for further cost.

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